

Join our BioBlitz and see what biodiversity we have in the park!

- 1** Welcome Table in Courtyard
Available 11am-3pm
- 2** Vegetation Safari
3 min walk from courtyard
11.15, 12.15, 12.45, 13.15, 13.45, 14.15
- 3** Wonderful Worms and Super Soil
10 min walk from Courtyard
11.15, 11.45, 12.45, 13.15, 13.45, 14.15

- 4** Marvelous Minibeasts
5 min walk from Courtyard
11.15, 11.45, 12.15, 13.15, 13.45, 14.15
- 5** Brilliant Birds
5 min walk from courtyard
11.15, 11.45, 12.15, 12.45, 13.45, 14.15

Suggested areas to explore using the iNaturalist app
Available 11am-3pm

Once you collect a sticker from each station come back to the courtyard to complete your mission!

Brilliant Birds

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